

Mannich Bases Derived from 3-Methyl- Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-one

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3-Methyl- Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-one was prepared by the reaction of hydroxylamine with ethyl acetoacetate and the product subjected to Mannich reaction to give 3-methyl-4-arylamino-methyl- Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-ones.

VARIOUS isoxazole derivatives are reported to have antitubercular¹, antibacterial² and antiviral³ activities. They also act as amine oxidase inhibitors and are found to be useful in physiotherapy⁴. Cycloserine⁵, the well known antibiotic of isoxazole series is useful in the treatment of tuberculosis⁶ and leprosy⁷.

With this aim 3-methyl-4-arylaminomethyl- Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-ones were prepared⁸ by the exotic combination of groups obtainable from the Mannich reaction on 3-methyl- Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-one, to enhance the microbial activities of the parent compound. The methylene group at position-4 of Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-one is very reactive as it is situated in between two electro-negative $>C=O$ and $C=N$ groups.

3-Methyl- Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-one is prepared by the reaction of ethyl acetoacetate and hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of sodium acetate. The Mannich bases are prepared by the reaction of isoxazolone (I), formalin (40%) and aromatic amine in ethanolic medium at 0°.

cm^{-1} in the carbonyl region. Lowering of the carbonyl frequency may be due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between amino nitrogen and enolic hydroxyl group.

Experimental

All the m.ps. are uncorrected.

3-Methyl-4-arylaminomethyl- Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-one.

The key intermediate 3-methyl- Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-one was prepared by refluxing ethyl acetoacetate (1 mole), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 mole) and sodium acetate (1.1 mole) in absolute ethanol for 3 hr. Excess of the solvent was removed and the residue was filtered. The filtrate which is 3-methyl- Δ^2 -isoxazolin-5-one was directly subjected to Mannich reaction.

Since the Mannich bases formed in this reaction are soluble in alkali, the possibility of structures (III) and (IV) as the Mannich bases may be ruled out,

Infrared spectra of 4-substituted isoxazolones and 4,4'-disubstituted isoxazolones exhibit the carbonyl absorption⁹ around 1700 and 1780 cm^{-1} respectively but the Mannich bases prepared show a peak at 1660

To an ethanolic solution of isoxazolone (I), (0.1 mole) and formalin (0.5 ml, 40%), an alcoholic solution of amine (0.1 mole) was added gradually at 0°C. After 1-2 hr, coloured Mannich bases were obtained in each case and recrystallised from a suitable solvent, their m.ps. and other relevant data are recorded in Table 1.

